

**SpaceTeamSat1
Preliminary Design Document
Educational Unit**

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Version 1.2

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Contents

1. Introduction	2
1.1. The Education Module	2
1.2. Related Documents	2
1.3. Requirements	2
2. Hardware Overview	6
2.1. Architecture	6
2.2. Interfaces	6
3. Components	9
3.1. Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3	9
3.2. Powermanagement	9
3.2.1. EDU power supply	9
3.2.2. Raspberry Pi power supply	10
3.3. Sensors	10
3.3.1. ADXL345	10
3.3.2. TMP112	10
3.3.3. BMM150	11
3.3.4. BME688	11
3.3.5. L3GD20H	12
3.3.6. GUVA-C32SM	12
3.4. Cameras	13
3.5. Mechanics	13
4. Hardware Behavior	14
5. Software Overview	15
5.1. General Structure	15
5.1.1. Student Programs	15
5.1.2. Operating System	16
5.2. Scheduler	17
5.2.1. Programming Language	17
5.2.2. Testing	17
5.3. CEP Protocol	18
6. Software Behavior	21
6.1. Command Handling	21
6.1.1. Store Archive	21
6.1.2. Execute Program	21
6.1.3. Stop Program	22
6.1.4. Get Status	22
6.1.5. Return Result	22
6.1.6. Update Time	22
6.2. Error Recovery	22
6.2.1. Error Management	23

6.2.2. Data Corruption	25
Bibliography	26
A. Appendix	27
A.1. AP22815	27
A.2. PAM2306AYPKE	27

Contents

1. Introduction

This document serves as the preliminary design document of the EDU submodule of the SpaceTeamSat 1 (STS1) CubeSat. It states how the requirements, specified in section 1.3 shall be met. Section 1.3 also provides an overview of where requirements are handled in this document. As this document is fabricated at an early project phase, requirements and design may be subject to change, until they are reviewed and locked in at the future Critical Design Review (CDR).

The document is split into two parts, Hardware (HW) and Software (SW), it is structured as follows: chapter 2 lays out the high-level architectures of the HW of the EDU. Building on that, chapter 3 goes into detail structure of the EDU parts. The suggested behavior of the EDU is explained in chapter 4. Chapter 5 lays out the high-level architectures of the SW of the EDU. Building on that, chapter 6 explains the behavior of the SW.

1.1. The Education Module

The EDU is the CubeSat's subsystem, that collects different sensor data, which is necessary for the main mission. Furthermore, it allows students to carry out little experiments, with their own Python code on a Raspberry Pi.

1.2. Related Documents

This document relates to the following other publications. They may be referenced by the given short sign or the respective number throughout the document.

Short Sign	Document Name	Purpose
STS1PDD[2]	CubeSat SpaceTeamSat1: Preliminary Design Document: System Architecture	Mission definition and design of the CubeSat system architecture
STS1DATA[1]	CubeSat SpaceTeamSat1: Dataflow Game	Design of the dataflow from the ground station to the CubeSat and within the CubeSat
STS1EPSRDD[4]	CubeSat SpaceTeamSat1: Preliminary Design Electric Power System	Design of the architecture, functionality and usage of the EPS

1.3. Requirements

In the following section some basic requirements are described for the EDU. In comparison to, e.g., the Electric Power System (EPS) subsystem, the requirements for the EDU are described in short key facts. Note that the same documentation procedure as in STS1PDD is used.

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
1.3. Each Subsystem of STS1 shall be powered, via the CSBI, by a voltage level between 5 V and 8.4 V:

1.3.EDU.1 The EDU shall be operational at a voltage between 5 V and 8.4 V.

Note: The EDU is powered solely via the CubeSat Bus Interface (CSBI).

Fulfilled: In Section 3.2.1

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
1.4. The power generating subsystem of STS1 shall provide a voltage level with a ripple lower than 100 mV:

1.4.EDU.1 The EDU shall be operational with a voltage ripple of 100 mV or less.

Note: The EDU is powered solely via the CSBI.

Fulfilled: In Section 3.2.1

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2] 5.1.
The CubeSat shall have two bus connectors, which ensure communication between all the subsystems:

5.1.EDU.1 All communication from the EDU to other subsystems shall be done via the CSBI.

Fulfilled: In Section 2.2

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
7.1. The CubeSat shall be able to deactivate all systems not necessary for communication once a command is received to do so.

7.1.EDU.1 There shall be an electronic circuit, which allows the COBC to deactivate the EDU subsystem.

Fulfilled: In Section 3.2.1

Note: This circuit shall be controllable from the CSBI.

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.1. The CubeSat shall have several sensors integrated within the CubeSat.

10.1.EDU.1 The EDU shall have temperature sensors, a gas sensor, an accelerometer, a magnetometer and five UV sensors integrated within the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: In Section 3.3.6

Note: The UV sensors shall be placed on the outside, of the outside PCB's on which the solar panels are placed

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.2. The CubeSat shall have multiple cameras which are suitable for an operation in space.

10.2.EDU.1 The EDU shall have two cameras, which are suitable for an operation in space and positioned on opposite sites of the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: In Section 3.4

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.3. The EDU should be able to recover from a small number of cosmic bit flips.

10.3.EDU.1 The system shall implement measures to correct errors in its persistent memory.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.2.2

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.4. The EDU shall be able to gracefully handle errors.

10.4.EDU.1 The EDU shall be able to recover from errors originating from the operating system.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.2

10.4.EDU.2 The EDU shall not be affected by invalid communication from the COBC.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.2

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.5. The EDU shall be controlled by commands from the COBC.

10.5.EDU.1 The COBC-EDU-Protocol (CEP) shall be designed in a way that allows for the detection of errors during communication.

Fulfilled: In Section 5.3

10.5.EDU.2 During multi-packet communication, both parties shall be able to request a premature end.

Fulfilled: In Section 5.3

10.5.EDU.3 The EDU shall implement a command to receive and store archives containing python code.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.1

10.5.EDU.4 The EDU shall implement commands to start and stop the execution of student programs.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.1

10.5.EDU.5 The EDU shall notify the COBC of completed executions and pending results.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.1

10.5.EDU.6 The EDU shall implement a command that packages and sends the results of previous executions.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.1

10.5.EDU.7 The EDU shall implement a command that allows the COBC to set its system time.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.1

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
10.6. The EDU shall be able to deal with being turned off mid-operation.

10.6.EDU.1 Any information the EDU needs to send to the COBC shall persist after loosing power.

Fulfilled: In Section 6.2.2

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]
11.1. The STS1 mission shall comply with the mission related FYS Requirements [3] where it makes sense:

11.1.EDU.1 The EDU shall be designed to withstand, as a minimum, a non-operational temperature range of -15°C – 60°C .

Fulfilled: In Chapter 3

11.1.EDU.2 The EDU shall withstand a relative humidity level in the range of 25-75%.

Fulfilled: In ??

Note: In case more stringent humidity levels are required, it is advised to notify European Space Agency (ESA) as early as possible.

The following subsystem requirements are deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement [2]

11.2. The STS1 mission shall comply with the mission related FYS Requirements [3] where it makes sense:

11.2.EDU.1 The EDU shall have a minimum of two temperature sensors inside the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: In Section [3.3.2](#)

2. Hardware Overview

This chapter shall give an overview of the proposed architecture, in order to give a preliminary understanding of the EDU components, and thus, the sectioning of this document.

2.1. Architecture

For the EDU a trivial non-redundant design was chosen. The main components of the subsystem can be seen in fig. 2.2. As the brain a Raspberry Pi CM 3+ is used, most of the sensors the Raspberry Pi is connected to is placed on the same PCB as the Raspberry Pi. Same as every PCB of the electronic main stack, the outline of the EDU subsystem is defined by a template [1]. The only change to this template is that the CSBI on the X+ side of the CubeSat is removed, this can be seen in fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1.: EDU PCB template.

2.2. Interfaces

The EDU has an interface to the CSBI X-, where it gets the operational power from the EPS and can exchange data with the Communication and on-board Computer (COBC) and the EPS, see table 2.1. Furthermore, the EDU is also connected to the other sensors on the solar panel PCB's via an I2C Bus.

To fulfill requirement 10.2.EDU.1 there are also two camera connectors on the EDU submodule. Those cameras are mechanically mounted to the CubeSat structure and electrically connected to the EDU

PCB via some kind of cable. Due to the lack of space inside the CubeSat, the connectors between the cameras and the EDU subsystem will be a flexible Printed Circuit Board (PCB). This PCB will connect and be used as an adapter between the camera and the EDU.

Figure 2.2.: Block schematic of the EDU.

CSBI Header X- V2

	Pin	Function	Used in Subsystem
1	2	GND	
3	4	GND	
5	6	VBUS	EPS, COBC, EDU
7	8	VBUS	EPS, COBC, EDU
9	10	GND	
11	12	EDU_SPI_CS3	EPS, EDU
13	14	EDU_SPI_CS2	EPS, EDU
15	16	EDU_SPI_CS1	EPS, EDU
17	18	EDU_SPI_MISO	EPS, EDU
19	20	EDU_SPI_MOSI	EPS, EDU
21	22	EDU_SPI_CLK	EPS, EDU
23	24	GND	
25	26	SPARE_1	
27	28	SPARE_2	
29	30	SPARE_3	
31	32	EDU_Boot_Pin	COBC, EDU
33	34	GND	
35	36	EDU_HEARTBEAT	COBC, EDU
37	38	EDU_UPDATE	COBC, EDU
39	40	EDU_EN	COBC, EDU
41	42	GND	
43	44	UART_COBC_EDU_RX	COBC, EDU
45	46	UART_COBC_EDU_TX	COBC, EDU
47	48	GND	
49	50	GND	

Table 2.1.: The definition of Version 2 of the CSBI header in X- direction.

3. Components

This chapter focuses on the technological details and describes the EDU components. The components of the EDU consist of the Raspberry Pi, see section 3.1, the power supply, see section 3.2, the sensors, see section 3.3, and the cameras, see section 3.4. The sections in this chapter first give an overview of the respective subject. Design decisions, based on that information, is then discussed in section 3.5.

To fulfill requirement item 1.3.EDU.1, an operational temperature between -15°C and 60°C shall be guaranteed. Due to this requirement, every electrical component must fulfill the operational temperature.

3.1. Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3

3.2. Powermanagement

The EDU subsystem receives the needed electrical power from the EPS, over the CSBI.

3.2.1. EDU power supply

To fulfill requirements item 1.3.EDU.1 and item 1.4.EDU.1, there shall be an electrical circuit, which allows to power the EDU subsystem reliable from the CSBI.

Due to the fact, that the supplied voltage over the CSBI is between 5 V and 8.4 V, with a ripple of 100 mV, an electrical circuit is required, which provides a constant supply voltage of 5 V.

To fulfill requirements item 7.1.EDU.1 there shall be an electrical circuit, which allows enabling or disabling the EDU, if required. The EDU will only be powered, if the “EDU_Enable Pin”, on the CSBI, is pulled logically high.

Figure 3.1.: Schematic MP28167GQ

3.2.2. Raspberry Pi power supply

The Raspberry Pi CM 3+ needs voltage levels of 5 V, 3.3 V and 1.8 V to be operational. The 5 V will be provided from the Buck converter in section 3.2.1. To deliver the 3.3 V and 1.8 V a 2-channel step down converter, see appendix A.2, will be used. This kind of DC/DC is used on the most Raspberry Pi development boards.

Figure 3.2.: Schematic PAM2306AYPKE

3.3. Sensors

To fulfill requirement item 10.1.EDU.1, there are following sensors on the EDU submodule. What sensors STS1 has is described in section 3.3.1 to section 3.3.6. The location of them is described in section 3.5.

3.3.1. ADXL345

ADXL345	
Sensor type	Accelerometer
voltage	3.3 V
current	23 μ A
Interface	I2C
Address	0x53
Company	Analog Devices

Table 3.1.: ADXL345 Hardfacts

Figure 3.3.: ADXL345 Schematic

3.3.2. TMP112

TMP112	
Sensor type	Temperature
voltage	3.3 V
current	10 μ A
Interface	I2C
Address	0x48
Company	TI

Table 3.2.: TMP112 Hardfacts

Figure 3.4.: TMP112 Schematic

3.3.3. BMM150

BMM150	
Sensor type	Magnetometer
voltage	3.3 V
current	800 μ A
Interface	I2C
Address	0x10
Company	Bosch Sensortec

Table 3.3.: BMM150 Hardfacts

Figure 3.5.: BMM150 Schematic

3.3.4. BME688

BME688	
Sensor type	Gas
voltage	3.3 V
current	12 mA
Interface	I2C
Address	0x76
Company	Bosch Sensortec

Table 3.4.: BME688 Hardfacts

Figure 3.6.: BME688 Schematic

3.3.5. L3GD20H

L3GD20H	
Sensor type	Gyroscope
voltage	3.3 V
current	5 mA
Interface	I2C
Address	0x6A
Company	STMicroelectronics

Table 3.5.: L3GD20H Hardfacts

Figure 3.7.: L3GD20H Schematic

3.3.6. GUA-C32SM

The GUA-C32SM [??] is a UVA Sensor, which will be placed on the outside panels of the CubeSat. EDU subsystem has six connectors on it, to communicate over I2C with the sensors on each site of the cube.[5]

GUA-C32SM	
Sensor type	UV Sensor
voltage	3.3 V
current	150 μ A
Interface	I2C
Address	0x39
Company	GENUV

Table 3.6.: GUA32-CSM Hardfacts

Figure 3.8.: GUA32-CSM Schematic

Due to the fact, that the sensor is only produced with one address, but every I2C Bus subscriber needs his own identical address, an I2C-Switch will be necessary. An I2C-Switch works like a multiplexer and connects only one sensor at time. The chosen I2C Switch, see ??, is from the company NXP Semiconductors. Two of them will be needed, because one has four channels.

PCA9546APW	
Part type	I2C Multiplexer
voltage	3.3 V
current	16 μ A
Interface	I2C
Address	0x70 - 0x77
Company	NXP Semiconductors

Table 3.7.: PCA9546APW Hardfacts

Figure 3.9.: PCA9546APW Schematic

3.4. Cameras

To fulfill requirement item [10.2.EDU.1](#), two cameras, which shall be operational in space, shall be implemented in CubeSat. The chosen camera sensors are IMX519 modules from Sony, which are placed on opposite sites of the surrounding aluminum structure. Due to this, a connection between EDU and the two camera modules is required. The hardware interface is a 22 pole PCB connector, which requires to be placed on the edge of the subsystem. As a consequence of the short flexible camera PCB an extension will be required, which will be a self-made flexible PCB with the required connectors placed on it.

3.5. Mechanics

The following section explains the mechanical structures of the EDU.

Most of the EDU's components will be placed directly on the main EDU PCB. Some sensors, like four UV and the four Temperature sensors, are placed on the CubeSat's outside PCBs. The template of the main EDU PCB is defined in a GitHub repository [6].

Furthermore, the Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3+ (RPi), which is plugged into a horizontal SODIMM 200, will also be fixed with two M2 screws. The screws are responsible for the RPi not coming out of the SODIMM connector.

To make every mission necessary connector easily accessible, they are all placed at the edge of the EDU PCB. Only development and debugging interfaces, which are only used for easier development, are placed inside the PCB. These connectors will not be assembled on flight-ready hardware.

4. Hardware Behavior

Subsystem requirement item [7.1.EDU.1](#) demands, that the EDU is only operational if it is enabled by COBC by a data pin on the CSBI.

Due to Subsystem requirement item [1.3.EDU.1](#), the EDU will only power up, if a voltage between 5 V and 8.4 V is provided to the EDU by the CSBI.

One result of the COBC PDD was that during the expected lifetime, a doubling of the required current of the individual IC's is to be expected. This means the latch-up protection must be designed for twice the current specified in the data sheet. The latch-up protection will be implemented in the next version of the EDU subsystem.

5. Software Overview

This chapter explains the test regimes that shall execute, in order to verify the fulfillment of the requirements. As this document is written in an early design phase, the test regimens may not be complete yet and may be expanded later on.

5.1. General Structure

The EDUs main objective, is to execute student programs. This includes the ability to receive archives containing them and return the results they generate. The EDU is controlled by the COBC. This means it only acts when instructed to do so.

The main control flow is therefore rather simple. The EDU needs to wait for commands sent by the COBC, parse and execute them. Only during the execution of a student program, a separate control flow is required, which supervises said programs timeout.

5.1.1. Student Programs

Structure

The student programs must be supplied as a ZIP file, which contains a file named `main.py` at its top-level. This is the entry point for the program and will be executed by the scheduler. The archive may contain other files that are necessary (e.g. additional Python modules, lookup tables), as long as it does not exceed a total size of 1 MiB¹.

The archive is unpacked into a directory, which is also the working space for the program. It is free to create arbitrary subdirectories and files in this space, up until the directory reaches a total size of 128 MiB². The only limitation is the special path for results is detailed below.

As the interpreter is called from within the program's directory, this is also the current working directory of the program. Any access to the file system shall be done with relative paths.

A directory tree might look something like this:

```
program.zip/  
  main.py  
  results/  
    0  
    1  
    ...  
  [util.py]
```

¹A random sample of Python source code files from popular packages resulted in an average ZIP compression ratio of 0.31 ($s = 0.1, n = 23$), which would allow each student program to upload slightly more than 3 MiB worth of source code.

²Assuming 16 GiB of disk space available to student programs, divided by 100 participating schools, equals 163 MiB, which is rounded down to the nearest power of 2.

```
[module]/  
    [extra.py]
```

Library Support

The EDU provides a number of preinstalled libraries to work with. This preliminary list is non-exhaustive:

- `numpy`
- `scipy`
- `pandas`
- `statsmodels`
- `python-dateutil`
- `isodate`
- `csv`
- `attrs`
- Sensor libraries (TODO)
- Geospatial analysis
- ...
- ...

Results

The program will be executed with a command akin to `python main.py <Timestamp>`, where `<Timestamp>` is an integer that contains the seconds since epoch at which the program is meant to be executed. It also identifies the result directory for each run, which is where all outputs of the program need to be stored. It is located in `./results/<Timestamp>/`.

Extended Configuration

For certain operations, the scheduler must interact with the student program. Therefore, the scheduler listens to the student programs `stdout` and reacts if it receives a control sequence which is composed of 4 bytes. Multiple control sequences can be sent back to back, however, each action is taken only once, regardless of how often it is sent.

- **No Compression:** `0x133c810c`
this sequence tells the scheduler to not compress the results. Results will only be packed into a tarball.
- **Enable Dosimeter:** `0xb101db6a`
this sequence instructs the scheduler to notify the COBC to enable the dosimeter
- **Disable Dosimeter:** `0x2fabc890`
this sequence instructs the scheduler to notify the COBC to disable the dosimeter

5.1.2. Operating System

As the platform is the RPi, a Linux Operating System (OS) is used. The Raspbian OS, which is generally used with the RPi, is sufficient during development. However, for deployment, such a system would not be efficient, due to the large amount of features which are not needed and the lack of dependability. We, therefore, aim for a more slim and robust OS, which will be constructed with the help of Buildroot.

Memory and Disk Management

The EDU expects the OS to enforce certain rules in its file system, which will be based on JFFS2. The operating system itself and the scheduler shall be mounted read-only, protecting them from any access by the Python programs. Additionally, each program should be sandboxed to its working directory. This means restricted access to paths outside and a limited amount of disk space. This could be managed by creating a user for each program and using the tool `quota` to set the memory size limit.

5.2. Scheduler

The actual functional requirements are handled by the scheduler. This is an executable immediately run after starting the OS. It is responsible for communicating with the COBC and executing the student programs. As the EDU is only acting on behalf of the COBC, its main loop consists of waiting for commands and subsequently executing them. These commands are further specified in the requirements derived from system requirement 10.5 and are described in Section 6.1.

When instructed to do so, the scheduler executes student programs by spawning them into a separate process. This process shall only be able to modify and access sensor data, as well as its own files. Should the program terminate before a specified timeout, this should be detected by the scheduler in a sensible amount of time. If it is still running after the timeout, it is killed. Any termination should be signalled to the COBC.

5.2.1. Programming Language

Due to the required robustness and performance of the scheduler, we decided on using a systems level programming language. After detailed consideration, we decided on **Rust**. It brings two main advantages compared to contenders like C++. For one there are modern abstraction mechanisms like pattern matching or the question mark operator. These have already noticeably improved productivity.

Another strong asset is the languages borrow checker, which enforces ownership policies during compilation and through this, makes guarantees about not encountering undefined behavior in runtime and memory safety.

5.2.2. Testing

To ensure that requirements are met, the scheduler is tested regularly and thoroughly. A custom testing framework has been built, which allows us to easily simulate interactions with the COBC. It replaces the UART connection from the COBC and instead sends and checks against predefined values.

Numerous test cases have been implemented, covering not only expected communication but also invalid data and communication errors. They are derived from the requirements and the specifications for the CEP protocol in Section 5.3 and Section 6.1. Additionally to being used during development, all tests need to pass before changes can be merged to the git repositories main branch.

As soon as progress allows, the EDU will be tested alongside the actual COBC.

5.3. CEP Protocol

In this section, the protocol used for the communication between the EDU and COBC is defined. The two models are connected via two wires, which will follow a UART protocol as shown in Figure 5.1. When idle the line is pulled high. By pulling the line low for one bit, the start condition is asserted. A byte is then transmitted in MSB first order and terminated with a high bit. The baud rate is currently $115\,200\text{ bit s}^{-1}$, but might be increased if appropriate stability can be demonstrated in tests.

Figure 5.1.: Timing diagram of a single byte

On top of the UART protocol, a custom data link layer is built. There are two different formats of packets that can be sent, either command packets or data packets.

Command Packet

A single byte containing a small amount of information. The possible values can be found in table 5.1.

Note: While the values chosen seem random, they are selected in order to ensure a hamming distance of at least 4 between all commands. This will suffice for error correction. Additional possible values would be $0x1E$, $0xFA$ and $0x60$.

Name	Value	Meaning
ACK	$0xD7$	Acknowledging a valid data packet
NACK	$0x27$	Not Acknowledging an invalid data packet
EOF	$0x59$	Signals that the transmission of multiple packets is complete
STOP	$0xB4$	Signals that the transmission of multiple packets should be stopped
DATA	$0x8B$	Signals that the data packet format is used (not a command packet!)

Table 5.1.: Command packet values

Data Packet

A data packet is used for the transmission of large amounts of data, starting with a single byte header, followed by a two-byte length field that indicates how many bytes will be sent (this does not include any metadata such as the header, length or CRC). After the raw bytes, a CRC32 checksum is sent. It is only calculated over the data field.

Figure 5.2.: Timing diagram showing a data packet byte wise

The header field shall always be $0x8B$, which distinguishes it from the command packets. The length field, while 16 bit long, must only contain values between 1 and 32768, which is the maximum amount of data per packet. The CRC field uses the parameters as supported by hardware in the COBC: Initial value: $0xFFFF\ FFFF$, Polynomial: $0x04C1\ 1DB7$.

A data packet shall always be answered with either an ACK, NACK or STOP within at most 1 second after the transmission of the data packet is completed.

- ACK means the packet was received and the CRC valid
- NACK means the packet was received but invalid (either wrong CRC or unrecognized format) and should be resent
- STOP means that the packet is valid, but multi-packet communication should be stopped now

The following sections demonstrate the different types of communication that can take place.

Single Round

A single round is used for short commands, that do not elicit a response of more than success or failure. It is started by the master who sends a data packet. After acknowledging the validity of the data packet, the slave responds with one more packet, which must be sent at most 1 second after the first ACK.

If the initial data packet was corrupted, the slave only responds with a NACK and the communication round ends.

Figure 5.3.: Timing diagram showing a single communication round

Multi Round

In order to allow the transmission of more than 32 KiB, it is possible to send multiple packets in a row. Again, each data packet must be answered with an ACK to continue. The sending party is free to continue sending new packets and finally an EOF instead once it is finished. This should then be answered with an ACK or NACK, indicating if the whole frame was received correctly. Even if only one data packet is sent, the initiator needs to mark the end with an EOF!

After acknowledging the EOF, the recipient must send another ACK or NACK, which tells the sender whether the data was handled correctly.

Both parties can decide to prematurely end the communication. The sending party simply sends a STOP command instead of data, the receiving party sends the STOP instead of an ACK. As the packets do not contain information about their position in the sequence, communication should not be resumed but completely restarted afterwards.

During such a conversation, a NACK triggers an automatic resend of the last packet. After an EOF it means that the data was valid but could not be handled correctly.

Figure 5.4.: Timing diagram showing a multi communication round

Figure 5.5.: Timing diagram showing an interrupted multi communication round

Figure 5.6.: Timing diagram showing multi-packet transmission from master

6. Software Behavior

In this chapter, the details of implementation are discussed.

6.1. Command Handling

The following commands can be sent from the COBC and are answered by the EDU. They are sent via the CEP and all start with a data frame. The first byte of data will be called header and identifies the command. In the diagrams showing the command formats, black means COBC, blue means EDU. Communication, especially data and Multi-round data packets, is assumed to follow the specification in Section 5.3.

The EDU silently ignores any command that does not start with a data packet. This is done, in order to deal with noise on the wires. Any data packet, valid or not, is however handled.

As every data packet's integrity needs to be acknowledged, the first N/ACK packet always refers to this. The byte order is strictly little-endian.

6.1.1. Store Archive

Header: 0x01

Through this command, student programs are transferred from the COBC to the EDU. The first two bytes after the header are the program ID. This is an integer which is used to identify the program later on when executing. All of the following bytes are a ZIP archive, containing the actual program.

The EDU unpacks the archive into a folder named as the program ID in its archive directory. If a program with the same ID already exists, it is overwritten.

6.1.2. Execute Program

Header: 0x02

Upon receiving this command, the program with the corresponding ID is executed. The Timestamp is a four-byte integer which is passed to the program as an argument. The two-byte timeout value is the amount of time the program gets to execute in seconds.

The second N/ACK tells the COBC whether the program was started successfully.

6.1.3. Stop Program

Header: 0x03

Format:

This command stops a currently executing program from running. As for now, only one program can run at the same time, therefore a program ID does not need to be specified. If there is no active program, the EDU also returns an ACK.

6.1.4. Get Status

Header: 0x04

Format:

The EDU expects this command to be sent after it sets its update pin. It then responds with one of three possible statuses, wrapped into a data packet:

- **No Event:**
- **Program Finished:**
where the program and timestamp are the ones of the finished program and exit code is the programs exit code.
- **Results Ready:**
where the program and timestamp are the ones of the results that are waiting to be sent.
- **Enable Dosimeter:**
- **Disable Dosimeter:**

6.1.5. Return Result

Header: 0x05

Format:

This command requests a result to be sent to the COBC, which is identified by the program ID and timestamp field. Should the result not be available, the EDU responds with NACK instead of the data packet.

After the final acknowledgment, the EDU deletes the result file from its memory.

6.1.6. Update Time

Header: 0x06

Format:

This command sets the EDU's system time. The four-byte value sent is the number of seconds since epoch.

6.2. Error Recovery

While the EDU is not deemed mission critical, a failure of it would still imply a failure of our mission. In order to decide on how to handle individual errors, they are categorized according to severity and recoverability (Table 6.1).

Category	Description	Action
Nonrecoverable	An error that falls into this category, cannot be corrected by the scheduler itself, or it does not have sufficient information to return to a safe state.	If such an error is encountered, the EDU aborts the scheduler, writes as much information as possible into the log file and stops servicing the heartbeat pin. This should lead to the COBC forcibly rebooting the EDU, thereby putting it into a safe state. In Rust terms, this means that errors can be unwrapped to trigger panic.
Protocol violation	Such errors do not originate from the EDU, but imply a violation of the CEP in Section 5.3 or command structure defined in Section 6.1.	The EDU responds with a NACK as defined in Section 5.3.
External	Such errors force the EDU to deviate from its normal control flow, but do not imply a failure. An example would be a STOP condition as defined in Section 5.3.	Such errors are logged but ignored.

Table 6.1.: Error categories

6.2.1. Error Management

The following list contains possible errors that can occur during the operation of the EDU.

Low-level UART Error

Category: *Nonrecoverable*

Any attempt of the scheduler to send or receive data via UART requires fallible system calls. Errors are fatal to the systems service.

Wrong Packet Byte

Category: *Nonrecoverable*

When the scheduler is idle, it waits for a command from the COBC. Therefore, the first byte that is received should indicate DATA packet. If it does not, the COBC expects the scheduler to be in a different state than it is.

Invalid Packet Byte

Category: *External*

When the scheduler expects a command packet from the COBC but receives invalid data (e.i. a byte not specified Table 5.1), the fault is a bit flip that happened during communication.

If this happens while the EDU expects a packet it should respond with a NACK.

If it is only waiting for the next command, it can be reasonably expected, that the COBC did not send anything and that the data is noise that can be ignored.

Command Structure Violation

Category: *External*

If a command is received that does not contain the expected number of bytes (e.g. Store Archive without program ID) or an unknown command (i.e. the first data byte is unknown), the EDU should respond with a NACK and return to the idle state.

Multi-Packet Communication Violation

Category: *External*

If the EDU receives packets it does not expect during a multi-packet communication (e.g. the COBC answers a packet with EOF), it responds with a NACK and returns to the idle state.

Internal File I/O Error

Category: *Nonrecoverable*

In order to perform its function, the EDU needs to perform a number of file operations (e.g. store a received archive, create result archives, write its log). Internal in this context means, that the files are only used by the scheduler itself (e.i. not used by student programs). Any such errors are fatal.

External File I/O Error

Category: *External*

When a student program fails to create a result file, it is ignored.

Corrupted Archive

Category: *External*

If a zip archive sent by the COBC cannot be unpacked because its format is invalid, the EDU responds with a NACK

Unzipping an archive fails

Category: *Nonrecoverable*

If a zip archive sent by the COBC cannot be unpacked because of system error, this is probably because of some internal file I/O error and should be treated the same.

Student Supervisor Error

Category: *Nonrecoverable*

If any attempt to manage the student process (e.g. start, kill) or lock acquisition of inter-thread data fails, the scheduler stops itself and its subprocesses.

6.2.2. Data Corruption

As the CubeSat is exposed to a considerable amount of radiation, it can be expected that data will be corrupted. Appropriate measures need to be taken so that a single-event upset does not damage the EDU beyond repair.

Communication Channels

In order to protect data that is sent between EDU and COBC, the protocol devised in Section 5.3 features checksums or similar redundancy. Errors in communication with sensors are deemed inconsequential and should be handled through other means. (e.g. retransmission, outlier detection, ...)

Memory Corruption

Certain areas of memory of the EDU are more critical than others. While corruption in student programs is easily fixed by re-uploading, changes to the operating system could be fatal. A tool like *dm-verity* will be used to employ forward error correction on at least some parts of the operating system.

Any state information of the scheduler program is stored in the file system alongside checksums and reset upon encountering errors. Additionally, a dedicated recovery tool will be developed, which can attempt to reset the scheduler, should the need arise.

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A. Appendix

A.1. AP22815

[Datasheet of AP22815 Power Switch](#)

A.2. PAM2306AYPKE

[Datasheet of PAM2306AYPKE DC/DC Buck Converter](#)